

Application form: Open Science Infrastructure (2024) - full proposal

Section 1: Applicants

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Section 2: Summary

Proposed project title	<i>Next-generation publishing: Advancing the publish-review-curate model</i>
Project duration (in months)	<i>48 months</i>

English public summary

This project accelerates the transition to open science by enabling Dutch research communities to implement and adopt the publish-review-curate (PRC) model for open scholarly communication. The project focuses on creating user-friendly PRC workflows supported by interoperable infrastructures, making it easy for research communities to start using PRC. Existing PRC infrastructures will be used and will be adapted where needed. By setting up PRC workflows in close collaboration with research communities and institutions, the project supports broad adoption and strengthens the long-term embedding of PRC in the scholarly communication landscape in the Netherlands.

Word count EN-SUM (max 100): 92

Dutch public summary

Dit project versnelt de transitie naar open science door Nederlandse onderzoeksgemeenschappen in staat te stellen het publish-review-curate (PRC) model voor open wetenschappelijk publiceren te implementeren en te adopteren. Door gebruikersvriendelijke PRC workflows te creëren en deze workflows naadloos te laten aansluiten op andere publicatieinfrastructuren, beoogt het project PRC breed toegankelijk te maken voor onderzoeksgemeenschappen. Het project zal gebruikmaken van bestaande PRC infrastructuur, die waar nodig zullen worden aangepast. Door PRC workflows in nauwe samenwerking met onderzoeksgemeenschappen en instellingen op te zetten, zorgt dit project voor een brede adoptie en een solide lange-termijn inbedding van PRC in het publicatielandschap in Nederland.

Word count NL-SUM (max 100): 100

Section 3: Alignment with the scope of the call

3.1 Vision for the project and alignment with the aim of this call

Several open science infrastructures, such as [Kotahi](#), [OJS](#), and [Peer Community In \(PCI\)](#), are available to implement variants of the [publish-review-curate \(PRC\) model](#) for open scholarly communication. While these infrastructures offer basic PRC functionality, they typically don't meet the full needs of research communities. For instance, support for open peer review is limited, and interoperability with repositories, preprint servers, peer review platforms, and PID/metadata infrastructures needs improvement. To make PRC easy to use, PRC infrastructures need to be tailored to and integrated in the workflows of research communities.

This project makes a crucial contribution to the transition to open publishing practices by helping research communities in the Netherlands overcome infrastructure barriers preventing them from adopting PRC. Our goal is to set up PRC journals/platforms for at least ten research communities, thereby providing the foundation for widespread PRC adoption in the Netherlands. This is a critical step toward realizing objective 2.4 in the [NPOS2030 Ambition Document](#), i.e., making PRC the norm by 2030.

In line with the aim of the call, we will use existing infrastructures, make improvements to these infrastructures where needed, and strengthen embedding of these infrastructures in the broader infrastructure landscape in the Netherlands.

Word count SEC31 (max. 200): 200

3.2 User communities, challenges and needs

PRC is central to open science as it offers an open, transparent, and collaborative approach to scholarly communication. Yet research communities in the Netherlands face significant barriers in adopting PRC. A key challenge is the fragmented infrastructure landscape: infrastructures such as Kotahi, OJS, and PCI often lack interoperability with institutional repositories, preprint servers, peer review platforms, and PID/metadata infrastructures, limiting their usability and discouraging uptake.

To develop easy-to-use fit-for-purpose PRC workflows, we will align PRC infrastructures with the practices and norms of research communities, providing communities with infrastructures tailored to their way of working. We will work with a range of research communities, aiming to set up PRC journals/platforms for at least ten of these communities. Below we list some communities interested in this.

Communities interested in setting up PRC journal/platform:

- Citizen Science Netherlands Network (working on setting up PRC journal/platform)
- Journal of Open Aviation Science (commitment to transition to PRC)
- MetaResearch Open Review (MetaROR; PRC platform already live, but needs further development)
- Netherlands Bioinformatics and Systems Biology research school (interested in setting up PRC journal)
- Benelux Association for Artificial Intelligence (interested in setting up PRC conference proceedings)

Communities interested in learning more about PRC, potentially resulting in setting up PRC journal/platform:

- Netherland Institute for Neuroscience Data Committee
- Dutch Society for Cell Biology
- Centre for the Just City, TU Delft
- Institute of Environmental Sciences, Leiden University

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Individual researchers from several communities (e.g., artificial intelligence, social sciences, statistics) have also expressed an interest in working with us to explore what PRC could offer their community.

Additional communities with an interest in PRC will be identified in the course of the project. Open Science Community Netherlands, the Thematic Digital Competence Centres (SSH, NES, and LSH), and the university libraries will play a key role in this.

Word count SEC32 (max. 300): 300

3.3 Alignment of project with OS principles

Our project aligns with OS principles in the following ways:

- *Open access publishing.* Open access publishing is an integral element of the PRC model. To realize open access publishing in equitable ways, we will work closely together with diamond OA initiatives.
- *Open data.* While the PRC model has mostly been used for narrative contributions such as research articles, we aim to be as flexible as possible in the types of research contributions to which we apply the model. The PRC model can for instance be applied to openly available research data sets.
- *Citizen science.* We will work with at least one research community that will apply the PRC model to contributions from citizen science projects.
- *Transparent research processes.* In the PRC model, research contributions are made openly available before, rather than after, peer review (for instance on a preprint server or in a repository). To further enhance transparency, we aim to apply the PRC model also to research plans (akin to preregistration) and potentially to research proposals and data management plans.
- *Open peer review.* Open peer review is an integral element of the PRC model. Our focus will be on openness of review reports. Openness of reviewer identities is more contentious and will be an optional feature in the PRC workflows implemented in this project.
- *Open source software.* The software underlying the infrastructures used in this project is fully open source.
- *Interoperability and open standards.* To ensure seamless integration and broad accessibility, we will adhere to open standards that guarantee interoperability across diverse infrastructures.
- *Community governance.* Unlike many traditional journals, the PRC journals/platforms that we are going to set up will be governed directly by the relevant research community. The community will decide themselves how they manage their journal/platform.

Word count SEC33 (max. 300): 291

3.4 Access policy

The PRC journals/platforms that we are going to set up won't have any access barriers for readers and authors (no paywalls, APCs, etc.). One of the journals/platforms will focus on citizen science contributions and will pay special attention to accessibility for non-academic users (e.g., by publishing outputs in easy-to-understand Dutch language and by enabling citizens to participate in peer review processes).

To simplify and streamline access to PRC journals/platforms, we will investigate the need for [identity and access management solutions](#) that facilitate single-sign on and trusted access. Where needed, we will work with PRC infrastructure providers to implement this functionality and make it available to users at Dutch universities, universities of applied science, university medical centers, and research institutes.

All materials we are going to produce to support users in setting up and using PRC workflows will be made openly accessible in a sustainable way.

Word count SEC34 (max. 150): 149

3.5 (Inter)national ecosystem

The PRC workflows to be developed in this project are designed to interconnect with the broader international open science infrastructure ecosystem by building on and extending existing infrastructures such as Kotahi (used by eLife), OJS (used by many diamond OA journals), and Peer Community In (PCI). These infrastructures already contribute valuable components to the scholarly communication landscape. We will enhance their interoperability with institutional repositories, preprint servers, peer review platforms, PID/metadata infrastructures, and infrastructures for long-term preservation.

To maximize cross-border compatibility, we will align our activities with international initiatives such as COAR Notify, OpenAIRE, and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). To do so, we plan to collaborate with European partners of SURF, for instance JISC, CSC, and Knowledge Exchange.

In the Netherlands, interoperability with institutional repositories and publishing platforms is essential. To realize this interoperability, we will collaborate closely with Openjournals, the national publication platform for diamond OA journals, and with the Dutch Open Research Information Hub (for which the DURF and BROCCOLI projects are currently in preparation). Alignment and integration between our project and other infrastructure projects in the areas of scholarly communication and open research information is currently being investigated in the Strategic Plan Integral Infrastructure.

Word count SEC35 (max. 200): 200

Section 4: Feasibility

4.1 Project plan

Activities will be developed in four work packages, as illustrated visually above. The work packages have the following goals and outcomes:

WP 1 – Coordination and community engagement

Goal: To identify and engage with research communities in the Netherlands interested in adopting PRC and to coordinate with related initiatives. Expected outcomes:

- Community of practice of researchers, librarians, publishers, policy makers, and others interested in promoting PRC in the Netherlands, working closely together with Open Science Community Netherlands
- Identification of at least ten research communities in the Netherlands across all scientific disciplines that are interested in adopting PRC, e.g., communities currently running a diamond OA journal or a journal published by a commercial publisher (see 3.2 for communities that have already expressed their interest)
- Exploration of sustainable business models for community-led publishing, in close collaboration with diamond OA initiatives
- Coordination with UKB working groups Open Access and Research Support to embed PRC journals/platforms in institutional OA policies and catalogues

WP 2 – Strengthening infrastructures to meet community needs

Goal: To ensure availability of infrastructures meets core needs of research communities interested in adopting PRC. Expected outcomes:

- Analysis of the publishing needs of research communities identified in WP1
- Analysis of the functionalities offered by existing infrastructures that may be used to operate PRC journals/platforms (e.g., Kotahi, OJS, PCI)
- Analysis of gaps in functionalities of existing infrastructures that need to be filled to meet core needs of research communities identified in WP1
- Enhanced infrastructures that meet core needs of research communities identified in WP1

WP 3 – Strengthening interoperability of infrastructures

Goal: To strengthen interoperability to ensure PRC infrastructures are easy to use and seamlessly integrated in researcher workflows. Expected outcomes:

- A domain architecture for PRC workflows, including a mapping of core infrastructure services (e.g., repositories and peer review platforms) and agreement on technical standards; this will be based on architectures such as HOSA (Higher Education Sector Architecture) in coalition with UKB and UNL
- Connections with Open Research Information Agenda in the Netherlands and with relevant international initiatives (e.g., COAR Notify based on ActivityPub, Crossref, Society and Open Research Europe) to ensure alignment with partnering initiatives
- Innovation community to work on improving existing infrastructures like Kotahi and OJS by adding PRC functionalities identified in WP2
- Improved user experience of PRC workflow, e.g., single sign-on for researchers engaging with different publication workflow components (e.g., repositories and peer review platforms)

WP 4 – Support and training

Goal: To provide support to research communities in the Netherlands interested in adopting PRC. Expected outcomes:

- Support for research communities identified in WP1 to help them set up new PRC journals/platforms using infrastructures identified and enhanced in WP2 and WP3
- Training program for research communities identified in WP1 to facilitate adoption and use of new PRC journals/platforms
- Knowledge base to support research communities that want to adopt PRC

Timelines

This 48-month project can be subdivided into three partly overlapping phases:

- *Phase 1 (months 1-12):* In phase 1 we will continue to reach out to research communities interested in PRC (WP1) and develop a detailed understanding of the needs of these communities and how these needs can best be met by existing infrastructures (WP2).
- *Phase 2 (months 7-36):* In phase 2 we will work on enhancing PRC infrastructures to meet the needs of research communities (WP2) and on improving the interoperability of PRC infrastructures (WP3). We will continue to reach out to communities interested in PRC (WP1) and we will work with at least five communities to help them develop their PRC initiative (WP4).
- *Phase 3 (months 31-48):* In phase 3 we will provide further support to the research communities that started using PRC in phase 2 and we will work with at least five additional communities to help them develop their PRC initiative (WP4). We will also continue to reach out to communities with a potential interest in PRC. These communities may start using PRC after the project has ended, benefiting from the experiences and the outcomes of the project.

The chart below summarizes the timelines for the project.

	Month							
	1-6	7-12	13-18	19-24	25-30	31-36	37-42	43-48
WP1 - Coordination and community engagement	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
WP2 - Strengthening infrastructures to meet community needs	█	█	█	█	█			
WP3 - Strengthening interoperability of infrastructures		█	█	█	█	█		
WP4 - Support and training			█	█	█	█	█	█

Word count SEC 41 (max. 750): 740

4.2 Team composition

Name	Affiliation	Expertise	Role/contributions
Ludo Waltman	CWTS, Leiden University	Scholarly communication, PRC, open infrastructures	Project leader WP1 leader PRC ambassador
André Brasil	CWTS, Leiden University	Scholarly communication, PRC, open infrastructures	WP2 leader Project manager (WP1, WP2) PRC ambassador
Jeroen van Honk	CWTS, Leiden University	Scholarly communication, PRC, open infrastructures	Community manager (WP1, WP2)
Wolfgang Kaltenbrunner	CWTS, Leiden University	Scholarly communication, PRC	PRC ambassador (in kind)
Theod van Leeuwen	CWTS, Leiden University	Scholarly communication, PRC	PRC ambassador (in kind)
Irene Nooren	SURF	Scholarly communication, PRC, business development, community management	WP3 leader PRC ambassador Ecosystem manager Strategic advisor
Thomas van Himbergen	SURF	Open infrastructures, community management, scholarly communication	Project manager (WP3)
Till Bey	SURF	Information architecture, publishing infrastructures	Information architect (WP3)
TBD	SURF	Community management	Community manager (WP3)
Nienke Annemiek van Schaverbeke	TU Delft Library / TU Delft OPEN Publishing	Diamond OA, scholarly communication	WP4 leader PRC broker (WP1, WP4)
Frederique Belliard	TU Delft Library / TU Delft OPEN Publishing	Diamond OA, scholarly communication, PRC	PRC broker (WP1, WP4)
Alenka Prinic	Leiden University Library	Scholarly communication, digital scholarship	PRC broker (WP1, WP4)
Fleur Praal	Leiden University Library	Scholarly communication	PRC broker (WP1, WP4)
Jeroen Bosman	Utrecht University Library	Diamond OA, scholarly communication, PRC	PRC broker (WP1, WP4)
Giulia Trentacosti	University of Groningen Library	Scholarly communication	PRC broker (WP1, WP4)
Maria Constantin	Erasmus University Library	Diamond OA, scholarly communication	PRC broker (WP1, WP4)

Anna van 't Veer	Institute of Psychology, Leiden University Open Science Community Netherlands	Community development, scholarly communication	PRC ambassador
Jan Willem Wijnen	OpenJournals	Diamond OA, PRC infrastructure (OJS)	Publishing partner Infrastructure partner
Elisabeth Elbers	Radboud University Press	Diamond OA, PRC	Publishing partner
Beatriz Ferreira	Open Press Tilburg University	Diamond OA, PRC	Publishing partner
Paul Shannon	eLife	PRC infrastructure (Kotahi)	Publishing partner Infrastructure partner
Michael Markie	eLife	PRC infrastructure (Kotahi)	Publishing partner Infrastructure partner
Thomas Guillemaud	Peer Community In	Diamond OA, PRC infrastructure (PCI)	Publishing partner Infrastructure partner
Margaret Gold	Citizen Science Netherlands Network	Citizen science community	Community representative
Sanne Abeln	BioSB, Utrecht University	BioSB community	Community representative
Louise Bezuidenhout	UNESCO Chair, CWTS, Leiden University	Global open science community	PRC ambassador

Word count SEC42 (max. 350): 349

4.3 Risk management

Risk	Likelihood and impact	Risk mitigation strategy
Little interest of Dutch research communities in PRC	Likelihood: low Impact: high	Given the many expressions of interest already received, we consider this risk to be low. Nevertheless, if there is less interest than expected, we will shift resources from WP2 and WP4 to WP1 to have more capacity for community engagement.
Infrastructures unable to meet needs of research communities	Likelihood: medium Impact: medium	We have a dedicated budget to cover the cost of tailoring infrastructures to the needs of research communities. While this budget is sufficient to make modest enhancements to infrastructures, it is insufficient for major infrastructure improvements. Communities requiring such improvements need to find other ways to cover the cost of this.

Needs of research communities too diverse; insufficient capacity to serve them all	Likelihood: medium Impact: medium	We aim to identify a limited number of ‘PRC flavors’ that cover most of the needs of research communities interested in PRC. We will prioritize communities interested in these PRC flavors over communities with very specific needs that don’t match well with the identified PRC flavors.
PRC infrastructures cease to exist	Likelihood: low Impact: medium	We don’t depend on a single infrastructure, but instead enable research communities to determine which infrastructure (Kotahi, OJS, PCI, ...) best fits their needs. In the unlikely case in which an infrastructure ceases to exist, a community can shift to one of the others (although this may make it more challenging to meet the community’s needs).

Word count SEC43 (max. 250): 249

4.4 Budget

Material/IT Type	Description	Cost calculation	Total (€)
work performed by third parties	Working with existing PRC infrastructures to meet the needs of research communities that are going to adopt the PRC model. Costs are for an estimated 1000 hours of software development work for third-party services providers and PRC infrastructure providers.	1000 hours x 150 euro	€ 150,000.00
knowledge dissemination costs	Two community workshops for each of the 10 research communities that are going to set up a PRC journal/platform. Budget covers a time investment of 40 hours per workshop.	800 hours x 150 euro	€ 120,000.00
national symposium/conference/workshop organised by the project itself;	Cost associated with the organization of two national events on PRC as well as the 20 community workshops mentioned above (e.g., travel, rooms, catering, etc.)	2 x 5000 euro + 20 x 500 euro	€ 20,000.00

Total Personnel requested: EUR 1.149.853,00

Total Material/IT requested: EUR 290.000,00

Total budget requested: EUR 1.439.853,00

4.5 Budget justification

The budget reflects the goal of the project to create a momentum for PRC, engage research communities with PRC, and adapt infrastructures to meet community needs. The basis are the project teams at CWTS, Leiden University and SURF and the budget requested is for project coordination, stakeholder engagement, and strategic alignment. To get communities on board to adopt PRC, community management is an essential part of the budget. Community managers will engage with research communities, give presentations about the workings and benefits of PRC, and organize training sessions to help communities develop an in-depth understanding of PRC. Community managers also have a crucial role in understanding the needs of research communities and translating these into requirements for PRC infrastructures, which will then be handed over to the project managers for implementation.

We also allocate budget to university libraries that will operate as a ‘broker’ for PRC activities, acting as a liaison and supporting research communities within their institution in the adoption of PRC. In addition to the university libraries, we will also work with PRC ambassadors. These ambassadors are highly visible members of a research community who advocate for PRC adoption in their community. Ambassadors will contribute in kind.

Part of the budget is allocated to community development. This budget will be used to organize two national PRC events, one at the start of the project and one toward the end. The budget will also be used to enable communities to organize community workshops for promoting PRC. This includes covering part of the time investment communities need to make to organize such workshops.

Lastly, part of the budget is allocated to infrastructure development. This covers the cost of working with existing PRC infrastructures to make the infrastructure improvements necessary to meet the needs of research communities interested in PRC.

Word count SEC45 (max. 300): 299

4.6 Impact plan

Our primary impact will be on the way researchers publish their work and perform peer review. PRC will make scholarly publishing and peer review more open and transparent and also more efficient (by accelerating sharing of scientific knowledge and by enabling review reports to be used and reused without restrictions). The initial impact will be on the ten or more research communities that we will support in setting up a PRC journal/platform. We expect these communities to inspire other communities to take similar steps, leading to a much larger downstream impact. To engage with communities, we will organize two national PRC events as well as dedicated community workshops.

Our focus is on research communities in the Netherlands, but through their connections with colleagues abroad, we expect the impact of our work to extend to other countries. Through Leiden University's UNESCO Lab, we will also work on promoting PRC globally, using Dutch research communities to showcase the value of PRC.

We also expect a broader societal impact. One of the PRC journals/platforms will have a citizen science focus and will directly involve non-academic actors. More generally, we expect open peer review to contribute to strengthening public trust in science.

Word count SEC46 (max. 200): 200

Section 5: Sustainability and software management

Section 5.1: Sustainability plan

Sustained effort is crucial for a reliable long-term embedding of the PRC model within the scholarly communication landscape. Key outcomes of this project that need to be sustained are PRC support personnel, improved PRC infrastructures, and active PRC user communities.

By engaging with research communities, fitting existing PRC infrastructures to community needs, improving interoperability, and providing training, we expect to create a positive momentum for PRC uptake, which will sustain itself into the future, ultimately establishing PRC not just as a viable publishing option, but as the preferred publishing model for many research communities. This is supported by a strong institutional commitment to open science infrastructures. This commitment has been agreed on by all national parties, as set down in the NPOS2030 ambition document, and has been operationalized in the open science agenda of Universities of the Netherlands.

In WP1, we will explore business models for the long-term sustainability of the outcomes of the project. This will be done in close collaboration with diamond open access initiatives in the Netherlands and in Europe more broadly. Several of our (co-)applicants and cooperation partners are deeply involved in these initiatives.

Furthermore, we aim to embed user communities interested in PRC in existing national communities, in particular the thematic Digital Competence Centers. Infrastructure improvements will be integrated within existing PRC infrastructures, such as Kotahi, OJS, and PCI. All infrastructures are open source. Infrastructure enhancements will benefit all future users of the infrastructures, also beyond the scope and the timeline of our project.

To ensure the long-term sustainability of the outcomes of the project, the project is strongly focused on alignment with existing infrastructure standards, active engagement with research communities, institutions, and other stakeholders, and strengthening long-term governance and funding models. As a result, we expect the outcomes of the project to be embedded structurally within the national and international scholarly communication infrastructure ecosystem.

In case there is a need for an infrastructure platform to be provided, SURF will be involved in exploring sustainable possibilities. SURF will then apply the Life Cycle Product Management (LCPM) process, which reviews the business case, including the financial, technical, and personnel aspects of the platform or service. This guarantees compliance with privacy and security aspects. In addition, it ensures developments are done in close collaboration with SURF members and expertise from the SURF network.

Lastly, we emphasize that this proposal is submitted on behalf of all universities and has been unanimously endorsed by the university rectors. It is seen as important for all Dutch knowledge institutions, fully in line with previously established national ambitions.

Word count SEC51 (450): 427

Section 5.2: Software management plan

1. Please provide a brief description of your software, stating its purpose and intended audience.

We will primarily make use of existing third-party software solutions and infrastructures. Depending on the interests and needs of the research communities we are going to work with, we may use the Kotahi, OJS, and/or Peer Community In infrastructures, and possibly others as well.

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All infrastructures selected and components used will be fully open source. We will ensure that selected infrastructures have software practices that are transparent and accessible to the community. Any new code developed for communities in this project will be documented by the software provider and made accessible for reuse by the wider community. In case there is a need to maintain software at SURF or elsewhere, we will do this in accordance with existing good practices for software maintenance, which include regular security updates, comprehensive documentation, issue tracking, and consistent version control ensuring sustainability and long-term value of the infrastructure.

2. How will you manage versioning of your software?

All our intended third-party software providers will use a recognized version management system (GitHub, GitLab, etc.) to manage and track changes to their code.

3. How will you make your software publicly available? What licence will your software have?

Any software development will be open source and freely available under a permissible licence such as the MIT open source licence or the General Public Licenses (GPL), depending on the third-party software provider.

4. How will users of your software be able to cite your software?

Software of our PRC infrastructure cooperation partners will be citable from the repositories where the code is stored and using a software citation (if applicable).

5. How will your software be documented? Please describe your plans for: user documentation, documentation for future developers and for installation requirements. Please provide links to documentation if already available.

All our intended third-party software providers will provide user documentation in a README file that will assist users in understanding and using software's features and finding developer documentation providing detailed information about the codebase, database schemas, and APIs. These resources will be made available through tutorials, deployment and configuration guides, and thorough code documentation.

Example of Kotahi README file: <https://gitlab.coko.foundation/kotahi/kotahi/-/blob/staging/README.md>

Example of PCI README file: <https://github.com/pci-dev/pci/blob/development/README.md>

6. How will contribution guidelines and governance structure of your software be documented?

Contribution guidelines and the governance structure of all our intended software providers will be documented in Markdown files within the project's repository. The contribution file will detail how developers and others can participate, outlining coding standards, the workflow for submitting changes, and the code of conduct. The governance file will describe the project's organization, including roles, decision-making processes, and how conflicts are resolved. This approach ensures clear and accessible information for all who wish to contribute or understand the project's management.

7. How will your software be tested?

All our intended third-party software providers have a structured release management process with versioned updates, including major feature releases, minor enhancements, and critical security patches. All releases will undergo automated and manual testing, ensuring stability and performance. Quality assurance testing will be employed, which will include unit, smoke, functional, integration, security, regression, performance, usability, and GUI testing, guided by specific test cases derived from user specifications. An iterative testing cycle, combined with tools like checklists, automation scripts, code reviews, and thorough documentation will ensure high-quality software, enable efficient development, bug detection, and continuous process improvement.

8. How will you check that it respects the licences of libraries and dependencies it uses?

Our intended third-party software providers will maintain a detailed inventory of all dependencies and their licenses, analyse license compatibility, and implement procedures for attribution, code modification, and license header management. Automated checks and periodic manual reviews will be used to monitor compliance throughout development.

9. How will your software be packaged and distributed?

All our intended third-party software providers have defined packaging processes (e.g., Docker), specifying formats and dependencies, and detailing installation procedures. They will also provide information that covers distribution channels, deployment strategies (where applicable), and mechanisms for software updates.

10. What level of support will be provided for users of the software and how will this support be organised?

Users of our third-party software providers will receive pre-release notifications via email, documentation and or webinars. Security fixes will be issued as needed. For communication, the software providers will provide detailed release notes, user support for post-release troubleshooting, and personalised onboarding for major updates. Regular updates will ensure platform improvements while minimizing disruptions. Software providers will also provide release schedules and dedicated online support for users.

11. How do you plan to ensure long term maintenance of your software?

All our intended third-party software providers allocate sufficient resources, including personnel, infrastructure, and tools, to support ongoing maintenance activities. All providers provide robust version control and have comprehensive testing strategies in place, including automated testing and continuous integration to ensure software quality and stability. They also have detailed disaster recovery and security plans. The software provider shall maintain up-to-date documentation for users and developers and regularly release code and supporting documentation for their community of users.

Section 6: References

Section 7: Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.
- I have submitted a pre-proposal for this Call for proposals in ISAAC.